

Public Libraries as Living Labs: Co-Creation and Public Value to address Grand Societal Challenges

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Abstract

Public libraries are undergoing a significant transformation from traditional repositories of knowledge into dynamic living labs that foster co-creation, innovation, and community engagement. This article examines the living lab paradigm in public libraries, focusing on how participatory design, multi-stakeholder collaboration, and flexible, hybrid spaces contribute to the creation of public value. Drawing on in-depth case studies of the Library Living Lab (L3) and Bibliolab network in Catalonia, as well as Medialab-Tabakalera in San Sebastián, the article analyses the drivers of public value, such as early and active user involvement in co-creation processes, spatial design that enables serendipitous interaction, the development of staff skills to engage diverse users, creative metrics to capture intangible outcomes, and robust institutional support. It also addresses shared lessons on how public value is manifested in public libraries, including community building, and the promotion of inclusion, social cohesion, and diversity. The findings demonstrate that libraries as living labs can serve as innovation intermediaries, bridging sectors and empowering diverse communities to address grand societal challenges, with co-creation at the centre of their mission.

Key words

public libraries, Living Labs, co-creation, public value, community engagement, social challenges

Introduction

Public libraries have long been celebrated as democratic institutions that provide free access to knowledge, information, and culture (Kranich, 2001; Leorke & Wyatt, 2018; IFLA-UNESCO, 2022). Traditionally seen as repositories of books and guardians of collective memory, libraries have played a crucial role in supporting literacy, lifelong learning, and social inclusion (Hodgetts et al, 2008; Delica & Elbeshausen, 2017; Lo et al, 2019; Winberry & Potnis, 2021), or even as tools to support community needs and civil life (Gascó-Hernández et al, 2022). The digital revolution, the rise of participatory culture, and the growing complexity of societal challenges have prompted a profound reimagining of the library's role in the 21st century.

Increasingly, public libraries are being recast not only as service providers but as living labs where dynamic, user-driven spaces where citizens, librarians, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders collaborate to co-create, experiment, and innovate in real-world contexts. This approach values citizen involvement as a driver for social change (Hernández-Pérez et al, 2022; Vilariño et al, 2018).

This article explores the emergence of public libraries as living labs, focusing on how co-creation and co-innovation practices generate public value to address current societal challenges. Drawing on two Spanish case studies (Medialab-Tabakalera in San Sebastián and the Library Living Lab and the Bibliolab network in the Province of Barcelona), the article aims at gaining insights on 1) the existence of conditions that foster public value within these innovative library models, and 2) the presence of shared lessons on how the public value is displayed, that is, obtaining evidence on whether public value is manifested or perceived in similar ways despite the structural differences between these public libraries.

Conceptual Framework: Living Labs, Co-Creation, and Public Value

Public Libraries as Living Labs

Applying the living lab model to public libraries is a natural extension of their mission as inclusive, community-oriented spaces. Libraries already provide physical and digital infrastructure, skilled staff, and trusted environments for learning and interaction. By embracing the living lab paradigm, libraries can become “innovation intermediaries” (Toivonen & Tuominen, 2009), facilitating collaboration across sectors and empowering citizens to address societal challenges. It should be stressed the consideration of libraries as living labs rather than libraries with living labs (Fuglsang & Hansen, 2024). This means

that, in some cases, the library as a whole transitions into a more experimental space, rather than designating a particular or delimited area within the library to function as a living lab.

Drawing on evidence from 16 case studies of European libraries in different countries, Fuglsang & Hansen (2024) highlight that the concept of a library as a living lab is a “template” for developing new library services tackling societal issues and fostering civic engagement, adaptable to a variety of contexts and needs.

This shift in focus reflects a broader movement toward co-creation and innovation within the public sector, driven in part by the impacts of the financial crisis, the rise of digitalisation, and the rise of new models of public governance. In particular, New Public Governance (NPG) emphasizes collaborative, network-based approaches to governance, highlighting the importance of involving a range of stakeholders (including government, the private sector, and civil society) to effectively tackle societal challenges (Osborne, 2010). This perspective acknowledges the complexity inherent in addressing public issues and underscores the necessity of coordinated action across public, private, and civic sectors.

The Notion of Public Value

The concept of public value is central to understanding the broader significance of living labs in libraries. The definition of public value applied is dual, as outlined by Benington (2011). Thus, public value encompasses both the immediate benefits to users (e.g., access to information, learning opportunities) and the broader societal gains (e.g., social cohesion, innovation capacity, democratic participation). Accordingly, the focus is not only placed on individual interests (what people value) but also on the wider public interests (also in a long-term perspective). Our interest in this research lies upon the second meaning of public value, as it is closely tied to societal challenges.

In this setting, co-creation and co-innovation are essential for maximizing public value, as they ensure that services are responsive to community needs and that citizens are empowered as active agents of change (Bason, 2018).

Research questions

Public libraries may approach the creation of public value through a variety of strategies, reflecting differences in their origins, institutional missions, and the communities they serve. These variations are evident in the way libraries are established, their organizational cultures and priorities, and the specific co-creation processes and participatory methods they choose to implement. Despite this diversity, two central questions emerge that are

crucial for understanding how public value is generated and sustained within the context of public libraries, namely:

RQ1: Are there specific organizational, institutional and community engagement conditions that positively drive the creation of public value in public libraries?

This question explores the enabling factors within public libraries that influence their ability to generate public value regardless the different types of public libraries. The aim is to identify if there are conditions likely influencing public value understood as long-term societal transformations through library services.

RQ2: Are there shared lessons on how public value (as long-term societal transformation) manifests in public libraries?

This question seeks to uncover common themes, practices, and outcomes across different public libraries that demonstrate how public value is realized and experienced by communities.

To address these questions, two Spanish case studies involving fieldwork were conducted between February - April 2024 at Medialab-Tabakalera (San Sebastián) and the Library Living Lab–Bibliolab (Province of Barcelona).

Case Studies: Public Libraries as Living Labs in Practice

Background and context

Case study 1: Medialab-Tabakalera, San Sebastián

The fieldwork was conducted on-site on 28th February 2024. The research drew on insights from five interviews (four with front-end employees and one with a manager), supplemented by observational findings and document studies.

Tabakalera, which is located in San Sebastián (the Basque Country-Spain), is a striking example of adaptive reuse, having transformed from an old tobacco factory into a vibrant centre for contemporary culture. The building, which occupies an area of more than 35,000 m², currently houses a diverse range of cultural spaces and serve as a hub for artistic creation, experimentation, and public engagement.

Within this dynamic environment, Medialab-Tabakalera (ML-T, hereafter) emerged in 2019 as the result of merging two previously distinct initiatives: UBIK, the creative library, and Hirikilabs, the citizen lab focused on technology and digital culture.

By uniting these two projects, ML-T became a pioneering platform that brought together resources, technology, and knowledge to support learning, experimentation, and collaborative project development for all citizens, regardless of age, background, or expertise.

Guided by the motto “learn, create and enjoy,” ML-T reimagines the library as a “third space”, that is, a place beyond home and work that users can truly make their own and where they can meet and interact.

It positions itself as a catalyst for creativity and social innovation, empowering individuals and communities to engage in processes of collective learning and creation. ML-T not only provides tools and spaces for experimentation but also actively fosters local networks and communities, emphasizing inclusion and citizen empowerment as key drivers of social transformation.

Case study 2: Library Living Lab & Bibliolab

Fieldwork for this study was conducted online on two separate occasions, 4th and 26th April 2024. Data collection included insights from two in-depth interviews, which provided valuable perspectives on the functioning and impact of the Library Living Lab (L3, hereafter). These interviews were complemented by observational findings drawn from the Project Co-VAL^[1] case study, offering a practical view of co-creation processes and user engagement within the L3 context. Additionally, the analysis was enriched by a review of numerous academic articles that report evidence and critical reflections on the L3, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of its development, challenges, and contributions to the living lab paradigm in public libraries.

L3 was launched in 2015 at the Miquel Batllori public library in Sant Cugat del Vallès, Barcelona, and has served as a collaborative space for experimentation and co-creation, where community members and stakeholders jointly design innovative services and activities. Building on L3’s success, the BiblioLab initiative has scaled this model to a network of 227 libraries and 11 mobile libraries across the Province of Barcelona, offering services to 5.5 million citizens (including 2.8 million registered users) and transforming libraries into centres for creativity and participation. BiblioLab demonstrates how libraries can act as community builders and “*boundary objects*” connecting diverse groups and fostering social innovation through open, participatory approaches (Hernández-Pérez et al, 2020).

Stressing the ML-T & L3-BiblioLab differences

The structural differences between ML-T and L3-BiblioLab are rooted in their local contexts, governance models, and approaches to participation and innovation. ML-T is situated in a working-class neighbourhood and benefits from strong institutional commitment, with clearly defined roles for all participants. Its operational model is characterized by organic, non-interventionist co-creation (i.e. only acting when strictly necessary), which fosters a culture of unstructured creativity and cultural experimentation. Moreover, ML-T is deeply embedded in the local community and the unique setting of Tabakalera as a multidisciplinary cultural hub.

In contrast, L3 is based in an affluent neighbourhood and have faced challenges in establishing consistent institutional leadership, with some stages marked by a lack of clear ownership and a need to reinforce managerial functions. Their user engagement is more hierarchical, usually distinguishing between co-designers (Alpha), testers (Beta), participants (Gamma), and observers (Delta), and places a strong emphasis on public-academic synergies, with an increasing influence from the private sector. Moreover, BiblioLab’s model is defined by network-wide standardization, leveraging a distributed infrastructure of 227 libraries and 11 mobile libraries across Catalonia to scale co-creation opportunities throughout both urban and rural areas, and covering socially advantaged areas with more disadvantaged ones. This contrast highlights ML-T’s locally embedded, flexible, and community-driven approach versus L3 & BiblioLab’s broader, and networked strategy for fostering innovation and public value. Figure 1 below summarises major structural differences.

Figure 1. Addressing structural differences: ML-T & L3- Bibliolab
Source: Author’s elaboration

Perception of public value in ML-T and L3 & BiblioLab

Case study 1: Medialab-Tabakalera, San Sebastián

ML-T operates as a catalytic framework where public value emerges organically through synergies among diverse agents-citizens, researchers, artists, policymakers, and civil society organizations. By fostering structured yet flexible interactions, ML-T creates an ecosystem where collaboration, experimentation, and collective learning converge to address societal challenges and drive long-term transformation. In this context, public value arises from synergies driven from the interaction of the different stakeholders, giving rise to different forms of citizen/social innovation. In words of a ML-T member staff: *“Building up different communities of practice gives rise to different forms of citizen /social innovation”* [quote]

The Open Groups in ML-T are a relevant mechanism to orchestrate this. Open groups are self-organized, interdisciplinary communities which are focused on specific themes (e.g., textile innovation, citizen astronomy, or sustainable design). They are not merely discussion forums, but active spaces for:

- Knowledge generation: Collaborative research on topics like circular economy or digital heritage.
- Project co-design: Prototyping solutions (e.g., 3D-printed recycled plastic objects in project Precious Plastic).
- Community strengthening: Building trust and shared identity through collective action.

ML-T actively addresses unmet societal needs through two basic ways: first, by introducing new dimensions to cultural creation and, second by fostering social inclusion and cohesion. As for new dimensions to cultural creation, rather than following conventional approaches, ML-T offers *“a different way of creating culture”* [quote] where community members are empowered to participate directly in creative processes and knowledge production. This approach not only enriches the cultural landscape but also ensures that diverse voices and experiences are represented and valued.

On the other hand, the truly commitment of ML-T to inclusion and cohesion has been amplified by its location in a working-class neighbourhood near major transit stations, and the increasing flow of immigrants in the area. Nevertheless, when the institution opened its doors, there was some rejection from certain neighbours, who interpreted it as an institution detached from the neighbourhood’s needs, something like a *“UFO for*

smart people” [quote]. As projects and activities with strong accent on inclusion were rolled out, the perceptions gradually changed.

Finally, public value is perceived in complementary and reinforcing forms, as seen in the Garagune project. In this initiative, around 8–10 people with mental and physical disabilities from the Garagune association come together every Wednesday to participate in the Precious Plastic project. The group collaborates on recycling activities, using a grinder to shred plastic caps into pieces, which are then placed into vessels to serve as raw materials for art creation, such as paintings and sculptures. Through this process, ML-T achieves multiple layers of public value simultaneously: promoting inclusion by engaging people with disabilities in meaningful creative work, advancing sustainability through recycling, and fostering creativity by transforming waste into art. This holistic approach demonstrates how ML-T’s model not only addresses specific social challenges but also generates lasting cultural and environmental benefits for the wider community.

Case study 2: Library Living Lab & Bibliolab

The L3 & Bibliolab initiatives have played a pivotal role in “*democratizing access to knowledge and innovation*” [quote] within the public library system, making these opportunities available to a broader and more diverse range of stakeholders across various contexts. By promoting diversity and fostering participation from different community groups, these initiatives have helped transform the traditional role of libraries. The new range of experiences offered opens the library up to other types of library users, who probably otherwise would not visit it, and by increasing the possibility of user participation in joint projects with rich profiles.

Furthermore, L3’s collaborative approach has contributed to a systemic change within the libraries managed by the Provincial Council of Barcelona, leading to the creation of the Bibliolab network. As a result, all libraries in the province have become “*potential innovation labs*” [quote], opening up new spaces and opportunities for experimentation, creativity, and community-driven projects. This scalability ensures that the benefits of open innovation and inclusive participation are not limited to a single location but are extended throughout the entire library network, amplifying the impact on public value and social transformation.

Public Value in Public Libraries: Key Driving Factors

The transformation of public libraries into living labs is increasingly recognized as a powerful approach for generating public value through co-creation and co-innovation (Fuglsang & Hansen, 2024). As highlighted in figure 2, the engine driving this

transformation is the active involvement of diverse stakeholders in collaborative processes that shape services, spaces, and community outcomes.

Figure 2. co-creation & co-innovation as the engine for public value in public libraries and driving factors
Source: Author's elaboration

Figure 2 identifies several driving factors to spur public value that can be drawn from the evidence gathered around the two case studies. Four factors are more tied to co-creation/co-innovation processes, as they are more likely to influence the outcomes and results achieved, while the other two (institutional setting and management, and better metrics to capture intangible outcomes) are more transversal.

- **Involving stakeholders from early stages**

When stakeholders, particularly users, are actively involved in the early stages, they develop a sense of ownership and belonging, seeing the library not merely as a provider of resources but as a shared, co-created space that represents their interests and aspirations <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/user-engagement-vital-trend-modern-librarianship-onyebuchi-ekpolomo-tisbf> (Barros et al, 2023). This participatory approach increases the legitimacy of library initiatives, as decisions and services are shaped by those who use them, fostering trust and making libraries more relevant.

- **Front-line Skills to Deal with Heterogeneous Users**

Library staff must develop new competencies to engage with users from diverse backgrounds, needs, and expectations, so that professional practices need to be better aligned with citizens' concerns (Cigarini et al, 2021). This includes cultural sensitivity, facilitation skills, and the ability to manage collaborative processes, moving beyond

traditional librarian roles. In this regard, Gago and Rubalcaba (2020) have emphasized that, in the context of living lab activities, soft skills are the front-end employees' skills that are most demanded.

- **Multi-profile Stakeholders Engaged**

Successful living labs bring together a wide range of participants, including citizens, experts, policymakers, and private sector actors. The diversity of perspectives and expertise enriches the co-creation process and enhances the potential for innovative solutions. Particularly, Kine & Davidsons (2022) have stressed the role of public libraries as active partners in the quadruple helix model.

- **Spatial Design Matters**

The physical environment of the library plays a crucial role in enabling or constraining collaboration and creativity. Flexible, accessible, and welcoming spaces support experimentation, informal learning, and serendipitous encounters among users.

- **Better Metrics to Capture Intangible Outcomes**

Traditional library metrics are insufficient to capture the full impact of co-creation and innovation. There is a need for new evaluation frameworks and metrics that reflect intangible outcomes such as social cohesion, inclusion, empowerment, and community resilience.

- **Institutional Settings and Management.**

The broader organizational and policy context shapes the capacity of libraries to innovate. Supportive institutional settings, leadership commitment, and adaptive management practices are essential for sustaining co-creation initiatives and embedding them into library routines.

Driving factors for public innovation: ML-T and L3 & Bibliolab

ML-T and L3 & Bibliolab exemplify how public libraries can become living labs, placing co-creation, experimentation, and community empowerment at the heart of their mission to generate public value. Both cases reveal that the flourishing of public value is not accidental, but the result of a constellation of the driving factors and intentional practices highlighted before. Thus, it is interesting to know how these factors are manifested and perceived with particular examples in the two case studies.

- **Involving stakeholders from early stages**

A major example of the importance of involving stakeholders from the outset at ML-T took place during the inception of HirikiLabs (the citizen laboratory that was precursor of ML-T). Indeed, the first workshops involved a process of co-designing the furniture and the tools of the lab under the supervision of a technical team. As such, a pedagogy of co-creation was infused and a truly commitment from users built up because that was the way for users *“to start considering the lab as something of their own”* [quote].

In the case of L3, the library was incepted as the result of a proposal about citizens’ needs carried out by the Residents' Association of Volpelleres Neighbourhood. This grassroots movement, fuelled by a commitment to innovation and technology, sparked discussions about addressing the district's unmet needs, particularly related to public service delivery.

- **Front-line Skills to Deal with Heterogeneous Users**

At ML-T, librarians and staff are no longer seen solely as custodians of books, but rather as cultural mediators and technology facilitators who actively support and inspire community-driven projects. This shift requires a strong emphasis on soft skills, including adaptability to change, flexibility, versatility, and malleability, enabling staff to respond effectively to the evolving needs and interests of diverse user groups. Transparency and open dialogue with users are central to this new model, fostering trust and collaboration. The guiding principle is to *“be there without imposing,”* [quote]

Soft skills are the most demanding skills in the case of L3 & BiblioLab. Skills such as trust and reliability, flexibility and versatility, or active listening are considered crucial to spur co-creation processes. Also, other content/methodological-based soft skills, such as adaptability to change, analytical skills, decision making, or management skills are considered a priority.

- **Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration and the Quadruple Helix**

Both ML-T and L3 & Bibliolab act as intermediaries in multi-stakeholder ecosystems, integrating citizens, academia, public institutions, and private actors.

ML-T’s initiatives, such as ACTS (Art, Science, Technology, Society), foster interdisciplinary projects and have expanded services for marginalized populations through partnerships with organizations, like the religious institution Caritas.

L3 established a permanent working group of five institutions—including municipal authorities, universities, and neighborhood associations—to co-design projects like 3D Capitals^[2], and has partnered with companies such as Hewlett Packard to enable high-quality 3D scanning of cultural heritage. This quadruple helix engagement ensures a rich mix of perspectives and resources, amplifying the impact of each initiative.

- **Spatial Design and Staff Skills as Enablers**

The physical environment plays a crucial role in enabling serendipitous interaction and accessibility. ML-T's modular layout, with movable bookshelves and multifunctional zones, encourages spontaneous encounters and new collaborations. In the case of BiblioLab, spatial design plays a crucial role in fostering interaction, collaboration, and creativity among users. For example, in projects like the “*Cuinem Santa Coloma*” Gastronomic BiblioLab, the installation of a kitchen at the heart of the library is not merely a functional addition but serves as a physical and metaphorical hub for practical, creative workshops (Chavarría, 2019).

- **Metrics, Accountability, and Institutional Setting**

ML-T employs a theory of change approach, focusing on personal transformations (such as participants shifting career paths or developing new creative identities), while L3 emphasizes participatory feedback loops to iteratively refine projects. Furthermore, L3 has established a protocol to delineate actions, where all projects and activities adhere to a framework comprising three components: (social) challenge, action and return. The social challenge involves the lab's goal of creating social impact by collaboratively identifying challenges with stakeholders once their values and interests align. Actions are taken flexibly, without strict methods, and the results reflect the innovation's outcomes.

Institutional commitment is another key factor: ML-T benefits from visionary local and regional leadership, while L3's development was initially hindered by the absence of a dedicated manager, only accelerating with the strategic vision and support of the Provincial Council of Barcelona under the Bibliolab initiative.

Shared lessons on public value creation

Once the main conditions for driving public value have been identified, it is time to consider whether there are shared lessons on how public value is perceived and manifested in both case studies, despite the structural differences previously highlighted.

Indeed, both ML-T and L3 & Bibliolab have succeeded in democratizing access to resources, knowledge, and innovation. ML-T provides creative spaces and technologies (e.g., 3D printers, laser cutters, audiovisual tools), while L3 explores how technology can transform user experiences, as in Project ExperimentAI^[3].

Inclusion and social cohesion are actively promoted in both cases: ML-T serves diverse populations (including immigrants and homeless people) through different collaborative projects (such as the creation of blogs and podcasts), while L3's Bibliolab network scales inclusive practices across 227 libraries, reaching both urban and rural communities and people from quite different socioeconomic conditions.

Promoting social diversity is central to both models. ML-T's projects frequently mix different age groups and backgrounds, actively avoiding pigeonholing to encourage knowledge transmission and mutual learning. L3 acts as a "boundary organization", involving users with varying levels of engagement (from co-designers to observers) according to their interests and needs.

Public value is generated and reinforced in complementary ways. ML-T's Garagune project, for example, combines sustainability, inclusion, and creativity, while its *café repair* workshops blend skill sharing with environmental awareness. The Bibliolab project extends L3's tailored approach across the province, generating synergies through a distributed infrastructure.

Community building is a shared outcome of both approaches. ML-T's open groups and ACTS initiative nurture long-term relationships and interdisciplinary experimentation, while L3's projects, such as the Interest Group on 3D Printing, foster "communities of interest" through hands-on engagement.

Both models leverage citizen science, which is aimed at addressing grand societal challenges and inform policy decisions, thus bridging the gap between science and society, to help society navigate contemporary challenges (from climate change and sustainability to the ethical implications of artificial intelligence). ML-T's activities around environmental impact and digital storage, and L3's ExperimentAI project, exemplify how libraries can bridge the gap between science and society, placing citizens at the centre of dialogue and innovation.

Conclusion

Two central research questions have orchestrated our analysis on how public value is generated and sustained within the context of public libraries.

The first research question: *Are there specific organizational, institutional and community engagement conditions that positively drive the creation of public value in public libraries?* has been answered in a positive way. Indeed, public value in public libraries is driven by a constellation of interconnected conditions, as demonstrated by the two case studies.

Public value flourishes when libraries adopt co-creation and co-innovation as core methodologies. These processes must be orchestrated from early stages, ensuring that users and stakeholders are active partners in designing services and projects and involving all stakeholders across the quadruple helix (citizens, academia, government, and private sector). Front-line staff skills are also relevant, so that public library staff must evolve into facilitators and mediators, equipped with soft skills (to engage heterogeneous users), and physical and digital spaces seem to influence co-creation, and hence, the obtention of public value. Finally, traditional metrics fall short in capturing public value and, accordingly, creative metrics are needed able to capture intangible outcomes, such as the achievement of higher levels of inclusion or cohesion that are associated to societal challenges. As Bason (2028) has put out, developing robust, participatory evaluation frameworks that capture the full range of outcomes—personal, social, and systemic—will be essential for demonstrating value, securing funding, and guiding continuous improvement

The second research question: *Are there shared lessons on how public value (as long-term societal transformation) manifests in public libraries?* has also been answered positively. Indeed, despite the differences ML-T and L3-Bibliolab reveal shared lessons on societal transformation, such as the importance of democratizing access to resources and innovation. Furthermore, they both promote cohesion, inclusion and social diversity, as well as community-building and bridge science-society divides through citizen science.

All-in all, ML-T and L3-Bibliolab epitomize the shift of libraries from passive repositories to dynamic innovation intermediaries. By embracing living lab principles, they demonstrate how public value emerges from participatory processes, institutional agility, and community trust. Public libraries as living labs are well-positioned to address pressing societal issues, from climate change to misinformation to social isolation, and can enhance the library's relevance and impact (Mulgan, 2019).

Finally, it should be emphasized that the analysis is illustrative, being based on only two case studies; therefore, broader evidence is needed to extend these conclusions forward and to explore further research directions. Two examples of future research, which illustrate the benefits of libraries transitioning from traditional repositories to dynamic

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30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

centers of co-creation and innovation, are the integration of environmental sustainability into the living lab paradigm of public libraries, or the analysis of the role of public libraries as catalysers of long-term impact on community development.

() Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the European Commission Award-Nr. 101061516 under the title: LibrarIN (VALUE CO-CREATION AND SOCIAL INNOVATION FOR A NEW GENERATION OF EUROPEAN LIBRARIES). The author gratefully acknowledges the generous collaboration of Arantza Mariskal, Ibai Zabaleta, Eneka Fernández, Elisabeth Domínguez & José Miguel Valdecantos (MEDIALAB-TABAKALERA), and Fernando Vilariño & Oskar Hernández (LIBRARY LIVING LAB) in the realization of the different case studies.*

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